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Barriers to the Sustainability of Agribusiness SMEs in Nigeria: Structural, Financial, and Socio-Cultural Perspectives – Evidence from Akinyele LGA, Oyo State, Nigeria

Abstract

Agribusiness SMEs play a vital role in Nigeria's rural economy by ¹generating employment, livelihoods, and food. These enterprises are also vulnerable and fail because of an intersection of structural, financial, and socio-cultural constraints. This study analyses the barriers to sustainability of smallholder agriculture SMEs of Akinyele Local Government Area (LGA), Oyo State, Nigeria, and proposes key challenges with suggestions for establishing resilience. A mixed-methods descriptive case study was conducted combining online questionnaires of 10 farmers with face-to-face interviews of 20 farmers without access to digital media. Evidence reveals structural barriers like inadequate roads, irrigation deficiency, and insecurity, financial constraints of restricted access to credit, high input costs, and fluctuating market prices, and socio-cultural pressures of labour shortages, household obligations, and trust-based transactions as all contributing to SME dis-sustainability. In addition, policy shocks, namely the 2025 grain-import liberalisation and unpredictable input distribution schemes, also heighten smallholder exposure. The study emphasizes the need for comprehensive interventions in areas of infrastructure development, financial inclusion, policy coherence, and socio-cultural dynamics at the grassroots to enhance the resilience and long-term viability of Nigeria's agribusiness SMEs. The findings have significant policy implications for rural development, entrepreneurship, and policy-making in comparable contexts.

Introduction

Agribusiness small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) remain a mainstay of rural Nigeria's economy, producing food, creating jobs, and sustaining tens of millions of households. Agriculture employs over 70 percent of Nigeria's labor force and contributed 23.69 percent to GDP in Q1 2025 (BusinessDay Editorial Board, 2025). Amongst the sector, smallholder agribusinesses—typically family-operated farms or micro-enterprises are at the backbone of local production of food and rural livelihoods.

Despite their importance, Nigerian agribusiness SMEs are chronically weak and highly subject to failure. Estimates available put the percentage of SMEs that fail within the initial five years of operation at over 80 percent (Alo & Olatunji, 2018), a compound mix of structural, financial, and socio-cultural constraints. Recent shocks also underscored these weaknesses. In 2025, astronomically high input prices, uncertain labour supply, and low farm-gate prices reduced farmer incomes. The step taken by the federal government to liberalise grain imports triggered a sharp decline in prices of local produce, forcing most smallholders to dispose at a loss or cut down on operations (BusinessDay Editorial Board, 2025).

These issues are worst at the local-government level, where farmers are operating under rain-fed agriculture with limited irrigation access, rural roads, credit, and market infrastructure. It is for this reason that this research targets Akinyele Local Government Area (LGA), Oyo State, a predominantly crop-producing society in south-west Nigeria.

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Targeting Akinyele narrows the spotlight adequately enough to capture grass-roots realities tended to be smear in national-level research.

Existing literature pinpoints among the frequent causes of SME failure as weak infrastructure, limited credit access, inadequate managerial capabilities, unstable or poorly implemented government policies, corruption, inheritance disputes, and disorganized ownership structures (Babbuli, 2018; Eniola & Entebang, 2014; Oparanma et al., 2010). Nonetheless, less empirical research has documented how these constraints interact with local society and culture and recent policy shocks, such as the 2025 liberalisation of grain imports, to shape smallholder outcomes.

This study seeks to fill this gap in research through the integration of field data from 30 Akinyele LGA farmers with the literature base. The paper contributes to existing debates on entrepreneurship, rural development, and agribusiness sustainability, advancing policy-relevant recommendations to strengthen the resilience of Nigeria's smallholder SMEs.

2. Research Aim & Objectives

Aim: To critically examine the limitations undermining the sustainability of agribusiness SMEs in Akinyele LGA, Oyo State, and to recommend practicable measures for promoting their survival and growth.

Objectives

1. To enumerate structural limitations such as infrastructure deficiencies, irrigation deficits, insecurity, and market interference that face smallholder producers in Akinyele.
2. To examine financial limitations such as limited access to cheap credit, rising input prices, and unstable farm-gate prices.
3. Examine socio-cultural determinants, such as labour-market imperfections, household income diversion, trust-exchange, and gendered access issues.
4. Assess the local impact of recent government policies, particularly grain-import liberalisation and input-distribution programmes, on the productivity and incomes of smallholders.
5. Recommend focused managerial and policy interventions to enhance agribusiness SME resilience and sustainability in the case study and similar contexts.

Literature Review

"Business failure has been defined in a number of different ways across the literature, with terms such as closure, discontinuance, dissolution, and exit often overlapping (Cardozo & Borchert, 2004; Stokes & Blackburn, 2002). Pretorius (2017) defines failure as the point at which an enterprise involuntarily is no longer capable of obtaining debt or equity finance to arrest decline, thereby leading to discontinuance. In Nigeria, like in other factor-driven economies, failure rates are significantly high, with finance problems cited by over half of entrepreneurs as the major reason for discontinuance (Bosma et al., 2009). Interestingly, failure is rarely attributable to a single factor; rather, it is often a consequence of a mix of internal and external pressures, including poor managerial skills, inadequate accounting procedures, oppressive taxation, market fluctuations, and policy shocks (Berryman, 1983; Burns, 2001; Oparanma et al., 2010; FEE, 2004)."

1. Agribusiness SMEs' Contribution to the Economy of Nigeria

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in agribusiness are a key driver of Nigeria's economic and social development. They provide employment, enhance food security, and earn rural and national incomes. According to the National Bureau of Statistics, agriculture provided over 70 percent of Nigeria's employment and contributed 23.69 percent to GDP in Q1 2025 (BusinessDay Editorial, 2025). This underscores the strategic position of agribusiness in driving inclusive economic growth and poverty reduction, particularly in the rural spaces where other formal opportunities for employment are limited.

Literature consistently portrays SMEs as engines of innovation, entrepreneurship, and competitiveness (Eniola & Entebang, 2014). The enterprises facilitate local value addition since they link smallholder farmers to supply chains, processing industries, and distribution networks. Agribusiness SMEs in Nigeria not only supply raw food products but also support allied industries such as storage, packaging, transportation, and agro-processing. Their multiplier effect is therefore of critical significance to national food systems as well as industrialisation pathways.

Furthermore, agribusiness SMEs are key to poverty alleviation by providing a source of livelihood for smallholder farmers, youths, and women. Agribusiness SMEs provide jobs that reduce rural-urban migration and stimulate local economies. As noted by Babbuli (2018), SMEs are a significant contributor to Nigeria's gross domestic product and an important vehicle for entrepreneurial empowerment, although they face a number of challenges in operation.

Despite their inputs, agribusiness SMEs remain vulnerable to structural shocks and market instability. For instance, the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted input supply chains and reduced farmers' access to markets, resulting in massive losses in revenue (BusinessDay Editorial, 2025). Similarly, new government policies on grain imports have undermined the competitiveness of local producers, demonstrating how external interventions can rapidly destabilize smallholder livelihoods.

Cumulatively, the evidence proves agribusiness SMEs to be crucial to Nigeria's economic development, but their continuity cannot be guaranteed. It is therefore essential to make sense of the constraints they encounter in order to derive effective strategies that will enable them to survive and thrive in an increasingly challenging environment.

2. Structural Barriers to the Sustainability of Agribusiness SMEs

Structural barriers are among the most persistent challenges constraining the sustainability of agribusiness SMEs in Nigeria. Weak infrastructure, undependable electricity supply, insecurity, poor logistics, and volatile market conditions are some of the barriers. They all significantly account for low productivity and competitiveness.

Weak infrastructure is one of the most often-quoted structural barriers. Evidence shows that poor roads, inconsistent power supply, and poor storage facilities contribute significantly to business failure (Alo & Olatunji, 2018).

For agribusiness companies, the vulnerabilities mean post-harvest losses, transportation expenses, and low market access. Babbuli (2018) also identifies that the

lack of consistent infrastructure such as water and power retards SME development, particularly in local markets where small businesses cannot transport goods effectively.

Insecurity is the other major structural issue. Banditry, communal clashes, and farmer–herder hostilities have displaced farmers, razed lands, and chopped down production in the majority of states. BusinessDay (2025) approximates that Nigeria lost more than \$13.7 billion in agribusiness revenue from 2015 to 2023 due to violent confrontations in farm areas. The 2024–2025 crop seasons were especially tough, with higher insecurity in the like states of Zamfara and Niger forcing farmers to abandon their fields during key planting periods (BusinessDay Editorial, 2025).

Policy inconsistency also is a structural barrier. Spur-of-the-moment governmental decisions, such as the liberalization of borders to allow grain imports in 2025, resulted in over-supply within domestic markets, destroyed farmgate prices, and pushed numerous small-scale farmers to deficits. These policy shocks demonstrate how exposed agribusiness SMEs become in facing sudden external action.

To smallholder agribusiness owners, these structural concerns converge in daily action. Farmers report difficulties in finding trustworthy and reliable labor, high input costs, and depressed output prices, making survival increasingly difficult. In 2025, many farmers experienced the worst financial year in recent memory, as the cost of inputs far outweighed the returns from produce sales. This lived reality aligns with Alo & Olatunji's (2018) findings that structural deficiencies—including policy instability and infrastructural weaknesses—are major drivers of SME failure.

Scholars caution that business failure is not everywhere defined and words such as 'closure,' 'exit,' 'dissolution,' and 'bankruptcy' have a tendency to be applied interchangeably (Cardozo & Borchert, 2004; Stokes & Blackburn, 2002). Pretorius (2017) proposes a comprehensive definition under which an enterprise fails when it involuntarily stops being able to raise new money to arrest decline and need to be wound up or subject to judicial action. Within the context of the Nigerian SME, failure is more often than not financial, through lack of capacity to meet rising costs or generate adequate returns (Gaskill et al., 2019). Failures are rarely due to a single factor; rather, it is always an interrelated mix of internal managerial deficits and outside shock factors, such as infrastructure deficits or ill-considered policy decisions (FEE, 2004; Everet & Watson, 1998).

In summary, structural bottlenecks such as poor infrastructure, insecurity, and unstable policies significantly erode the viability of Nigeria's agribusiness SMEs. These must be tackled collectively through infrastructure investment reforms, security measures, and policy stability, or else small agribusiness enterprises will remain highly vulnerable.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study utilized a mixed-methods descriptive case study design to investigate the challenges affecting smallholder agribusiness SMEs' sustainability in Akinyele Local Government Area (LGA), Oyo State, Nigeria.

The quantitative component was an online structured survey via Google Forms to obtain demographic, structural, financial, and socio-cultural data.

Qualitative work included face-to-face interviews with farmers lacking smartphones and the internet, enabling incorporation of voices that are normally excluded from online questionnaires.

3.2 Study Area

Akinyele LGA is a society which predominantly comprises crop-farming individuals in south-west Nigeria. Farms within the area are predominantly rain-fed, and farmers are predominantly smallholder producers producing seasonal food crops. Current challenges in the locality include poor feeder roads, lack of irrigation facilities, limited access to formal credit, and susceptibility to farmer–herder clashes and theft.

3.3 Sampling and Participants

Purposive sampling technique was utilized in reaching active smallholder farmers residing in Akinyele LGA. 30 respondents were engaged in the study:

10 farmers completed the online Google Form questionnaire. 20 farmers were interviewed face-to-face with the same questionnaire questions.

Inclusion criteria were:

- Age 18 years and older.
- Having a crop-based or mixed-farming agribusiness in Akinyele LGA.
- Having farming experience for a minimum of one year.

3.4 Data Collection Tools

The standardized survey collected the following variables:

- Demographics: age, gender, education, years of experience as a farmer.
- Farming characteristics: type of farming, dependence on irrigation vs. rain, road access.
- Structural and policy-related barriers: market access, insecurity, impact of government programs.
- Economic barriers: credit access, input costs, produce price.
- Socio-cultural: labor availability, family commitments affecting farm income, trust in buyer–supplier relationship.
- Open-ended questions: farmers' perceived priorities and biggest challenges for 2025.

For offline interviews, the research team (led by Ogunmoroti Olapeju Esther) verbally translated questions into Yoruba where necessary for easier understanding by farmers with low literacy.

3.5 Data Analysis

Quantitative data of the online survey were presented with descriptive statistics (percentages and frequencies). The responses of face-to-face interviews were manually coded and integrated into the dataset to establish typical themes and patterns across all respondents. Both facts were combined and integrated in the Findings section.

3.6 Ethical Concerns

- Voluntary participation was employed, and the participants gave verbal informed consent before completing the survey or interview.
- All information was collected anonymously, without capturing any personal data.
- The study adhered to the elements of confidentiality, respect for the participants, and use of the data for academic reasons only.

4. Findings

This section presents findings of the survey and interviews among smallholder farmers in Akinyele Local Government Area (LGA), Oyo State, Nigeria. Data were obtained from 30 respondents: 10 using an online Google Form survey and 20 by offline face-to-face interviews with farmers who lacked access to smartphones or the internet. The combined dataset provides a window into the structural, financial, and socio-cultural challenges that hamper the sustainability of smallholder agribusinesses in the research area.

4.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics

- Age: Farmers were aged 25–70.
- The 35–44 age category (50%) predominated the online sample but the offline sample was composed of older farmers (above 50) years.
- Gender: Females dominated both samples ($\approx 60\%$), an indication that women dominate smallholder crop farming in Akinyele LGA.
- Education: There was considerable difference between the two.
- Amongst online respondents, 60% had a tertiary level of education and 20% postgraduate.
- Among off-line respondents, $\approx 70\%$ were not formally educated, and this points to a huge literacy gap.
- Farming Experience: The majority of respondents had ≥ 5 years of experience in farming, with a majority of the offline group having farmed for over a decade.

These findings indicate that smallholder farming in Akinyele is mainly supported by experienced farmers mainly women with diverse levels of education.

4.2 Farming Characteristics and Structural Barriers

- Farming Type: The majority of respondents ($\approx 90\%$) were farmers of crops; very few of them engaged in livestock or mixed farming.
- Irrigation: All 30 farmers relied solely on rainfall, making them vulnerable to climatic uncertainty and seasonality-based production shocks.

Infrastructure:

- 70% of the offline sample respondents cited poor farm road and transport connectivity.

Offline respondents reinforced the same issues, adding that poor feeder road conditions made it challenging to transport inputs and produce on time.

Insecurity:

Among the 80% of the online group that confirmed being affected by insecurity, 40% reported the impact was "very much" while 40% confirmed it resulted in stopping or reducing farm activities.

Offline farmers indicated confirming the same, reporting crop destruction and reduced

production as a result of farmer-herder conflicts, banditry, and theft.

4.3 Financial Barriers

- Access to Finance: Not one of the 30 farmers had utilized any form of government grant or loan for agriculture.
- Input Costs vs. Market Prices: Fifty percent of online respondents cited high input costs (fertilizer, seed, feed) as their largest financial concern, while the other 50% cited low market prices for produce.
- Offline respondents also grumbled about rising input costs and erratic produce costs.

Policy-related Problems: Farmers protested that although a distribution of subsidised farm inputs by the Oyo State government did occur, the majority in Akinyele did not receive any benefits since they were not registered with local farmer associations or did not know how to register. Others complained that inputs distributed in other LGAs were of poor quality or fake, further eroding trust in government programmes.

4.4 Socio-Cultural Barriers

Labour: Among online respondents, 70% struggled in hiring good laborers, particularly during peak seasons.

Home Obligations: \approx 90% indicated household or community obligations most frequently diverted farm income, limiting reinvestment within their business.

Faithfulness in Business Relationships: \approx 90% of all respondents to this survey considered trust "very important" in dealings with buyers, suppliers, and staff suggesting informal relationships and trust remain at the center of local agribusiness transactions.

4.5 Farmers' Priorities and Lived Experiences

Spontaneous opinions highlighted some persistent priorities:

- Providing cheap credit/loans and grants to purchase inputs or lease land.
- Input subsidy (e.g., fertiliser, seeds) and irrigation infrastructure.
- Greater security, including an end to farmer-herder clashes.
- Better farm-to-market roads and price stabilisation instruments.
- Inclusive and transparent government schemes reaching unregistered smallholders were also a priority for most farmers.

4.6 Summary of Key Findings

The findings show an intersection of structural vulnerabilities (poor roads, absence of

irrigation, insecurity), financial exclusion (absence of grants/loans, rise in input prices, low price for produce), and socio-cultural forces (labour shortage, family commitment, reliance on trust) as primary obstacles to the sustainability of smallholder agribusinesses in Akinyele LGA.

These findings validate past research attributing failure of SMEs in Nigeria to infrastructure deficits, policy inconsistencies, and management problems, but the case study is given a localized setting showing how such problems express themselves at the local level among mostly rain-fed crop farmers.

5. Discussion

This study explored the impediments to the sustainability of smallholder agribusinesses in Akinyele Local Government Area (LGA), Oyo State, Nigeria. The study points out that the impediments to these farmers' businesses are multi-faceted and embody aspects of structural, financial, policy-related, and socio-cultural problems—reflecting literature on small-scale business failure in developing economies (Berryman, 1983; Oparanma et al., 2010; Bosma et al., 2009).

5.1 Structural Constraints: Infrastructure and Irrigation

All the respondents had indicated dependency on rain, which exposes farmers to climatic risk and variable production in seasons.

The lack of irrigation facilities is consistent with Nigeria's national figure of <2% irrigated land (BusinessDay Editorial Board, 2025), which has been repeatedly cited as being a dominant obstacle to agricultural productivity and resilience.

Concurrently, weak rural road infrastructure and transport—cited by 70% of online respondents and corroborated by offline interviewees—prevent farmers from reaching the markets on time, hence causing post-harvest losses and price volatility. These results are consistent with previous research that determined infrastructure shortages as a structural factor leading to agribusiness failure (Ooghe & Waeyaert, 2004; Alo & Olatunji, 2018).

5.2 Insecurity and Policy Environment

The majority of farmers (80% online; same opinions offline) attributed insecurity—banditry, theft, and farmer-herder clashes—to a major spoiler, with some being forced to abandon farming altogether. This is consistent with the SBM Intelligence report (quoted in BusinessDay Editorial, 2025), which put that between 2015 and 2023, Nigeria lost a total of \$13.7 billion worth of agricultural revenue to farmer-herder clashes.

Further, policies such as government imports of grain and clandestine input-distribution programs were widely thought to be harmful, diluting market prices and discouraging output. All these are consistent with previous studies that point out policy inconsistency and ineffective application as causes of SME failure in Nigeria (Oparanma et al., 2010).

5.3 Financial Exclusion and Market Vulnerability

Perhaps most surprising was the fact that not a single one of the 30 farmers had received government loans or grants, something that had been advertised at state and federal levels. This implies a gap between policy-making and bottom-up inclusion, complemented by findings by Bosma et al. (2009) to indicate that financial exclusion ranks as a primary cause of small-business closure in factor-driven economies.

Moreover, high input prices (seeds, fertiliser, feed) and low farm-gate prices were the two most commonly cited cost pressures. Not only do these pressures tighten profit

margins, but they are also part of a cycle of stagnation and under-investment, echoing conceptual frameworks of business failure which emphasize cash-flow problems and a lack of working capital as primary causes (Gaskill et al., 2019; Pretorius, 2017).

5.4 Socio-Cultural and Labour-Market Challenges

The findings also reveal significant labour-market frictions with 70% of the internet sample reporting that it was difficult to obtain reliable workers, especially during peak periods.

In addition, ≈90% reported that family or communal obligations routinely siphon off farm earnings, limiting reinvestment in farm expansion. These informal financial pressures are not normally included in formal SME policy but have been found to be underlying constraints on entrepreneurial performance in rural African contexts (FEE, 2004).

The emphasis placed on trust within buyer–supplier relationships (≈90% of them listed it as "very important") again highlights the informal nature of rural agribusiness transactions, where lax formal enforcement of contracts increases vulnerability to opportunism.

5.5 The Gendered Dimension

The other major finding of this study is that women comprise about 60% of smallholder farmers in Akinyele but remain disproportionately excluded from formal credit facilities and government programs.

This is corroborated by previous findings, which point to the fact that women farmers face compounded disadvantage in accessing finance and security of tenure, driving cycles of subsistence-level production and vulnerability (FAO, 2022; Oparanma et al., 2010). Strategic interventions driven by women's access to resources are thus crucial to ensure inclusive rural development.

5.6 Implications for Agribusiness Sustainability

These drivers, individually or collectively, compound to weaken smallholder resilience. In accordance with Ooghe and De Prijcker's (2008) failure model, the relationship between general environment (policy, security, climate), immediate environment (buyers, suppliers), and internal management capability magnifies business cessation risk. The Akinyele experience bears witness that smallholder failure is seldom due to a single reason but through a patterned interaction of constraints.

Therefore, sustainable agribusiness expansion in such environments requires a multi-faceted approach: improvements in rural infrastructure and irrigation, security, price level stabilization in the markets, improved access to affordable credit, and the inclusive distribution of input support.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusion: The reasons for smallholder agribusiness failure and susceptibility in Akinyele Local Government Area (LGA), Oyo State, Nigeria, were investigated in this study. Founding its conclusions on 30 farmer responses (10 online questionnaires and 20 offline interviews), the research found that rain-fed agriculture, high input costs, low farm-gate prices, weak rural infrastructure, insecurity, discrimination of farmers in

government support programs, and household cash flow pressures all come together to undermine the sustainability of smallholder farming enterprises.

The data supports the multi-causal nature of agribusiness failure highlighted in earlier studies (Gaskill et al., 2019; Pretorius, 2017; Ooghe & De Pijcker, 2008), which illustrates how financial, structural, and socio-political constraints interact to entrap smallholders in productivity traps of low intensities and exposure.

Notably, the report sheds light on the gender dimension of rural farming, wherein women-making up approximately 60% of farmers in the sample population-are disproportionately excluded from formal credit and policy protection.

The Akinyele case thus mirrors broader Nigerian smallholder agricultural challenges and highlights the need for country-specific responses differentiated to overcome systemic constraints rather than piecemeal support interventions.

6.2 Recommendations

To enhance the resilience and sustainability of smallholder agribusinesses in Akinyele and other such settings, the following are recommended:

1. **Enhance Rural Infrastructure and Irrigation:** Prioritize rural feeder road construction and maintenance to facilitate timely market access and minimize post-harvest loss. Increase affordable, small-scale irrigation schemes to minimize rainfall dependence, employing community-based approaches and public-private partnerships.
2. **Improve Security for Farmlands:** Establish a local agro-security task force, as suggested in the BusinessDay Editorial (2025), with complementarities of current state security units to counter farmer-herder clashes, theft, and sabotage. Strengthen community-level conflict resolution committees to settle land-use disputes and improve stakeholders' confidence.
3. **Improve Financial Inclusion:** Design decentralised, open loan and grant facilities for unregistered or semi-formal smallholders through cooperative platforms and mobile banking. Promote micro-insurance schemes for crop and animal losses, and especially for covering women-managed farms.
4. **Stabilise Farm-Gate Prices and Strengthen Markets:** Offer minimum price support or buffer-stock buying schemes for major crops to insulate farmers from price meltdowns caused by imports of grain or surpluses. Encourage aggregation centres and farmers' cooperatives to increase collective bargaining and reduce the share of exploitative middlemen.
5. **Support Women Farmers:** Ensure that no less than 50% of future agricultural input subsidies, grants, and training schemes directly benefit women smallholders. Simplify land documentation and collateral processes to enhance access by women to credit and productive resources.
6. **Enable Farmer Education and Record-Keeping:** Work with local extension services and NGOs to provide basic training in record-keeping, business planning, and financial education. Enable the utilization of digital farm records and mobile-based advisory services for improved farm management.

7. Inclusive Implementation of Policy: Reorient grassroots sensitisation and registration exercises to ensure genuine farmers, rather than politically powerful middlemen, benefit from input-distribution programs. Involve local farmer organisations in monitoring and feedback mechanisms to increase transparency and accountability of government interventions.

6.3 Future Research

Other research could seek to estimate modelling of economic loss due to insecurity and policy shocks at LGA levels. Comparative analyses in some LGAs in Oyo State or any state could also be necessary to determine scalable solutions to different agro-ecological zones.

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